

ГОТОВНІСТЬ ЛІКАРІВ ТЕРАПЕВТИЧНОГО ПРОФІЛЮ ДО ПРОВЕДЕННЯ НЕВІДКЛАДНИХ МЕДИЧНИХ ЗАХОДІВ НА МІСЦІ ПОДІЇ

READINESS OF THERAPEUTIC DOCTORS' TO PERFORM EMERGENCY MEDICAL MEASURES AT THE SCENE

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Introduction. During the last years, it has been observed the worldwide tendency to regular creation, upgrade, and implementation of emergency care protocols at the prehospital stage in the medical practice. A huge role is given to the methods of doctors' simulation preparedness in case of emergency care at the scene. Modern doctors' preparedness requires practicing the resuscitation in the simulation centers on the specific dummies or devices without the risk of making any harm to the patient, developing the ability to make the quick and correct decisions, and conducting all necessary manipulations and interferences without any mistakes. According to the professional literature, it is usually observed the lack of practical skills concerning emergency care at the scene of an accident among therapeutic doctors'. Nowadays, one of the most important tasks in undergraduate and postgraduate medical education is the creation of simulation centers for quality training of highly qualified specialists, including emergency medical care.

Aim of work. The aim of the given investigation is the evaluation of the professional therapeutic doctors' competency in providing emergency medical care at the scene in accordance with the latest recommendations of the European Resuscitation Council (2021) and American Heart Association (2020).

Results. According to tests conducted in the 2017-2018s among therapeutic doctors about their abilities in the resuscitation conducting, it was revealed that only 52% were able to diagnose the state of clinical death; 63% - were able to perform chest compression; 15% were able to provide the opening of airways; extremely low was the numbers of those who were able to use AED and ventilation – 5% and 9% correspondently.

Conclusion. Therefore, one of the key tasks of modern medical simulative education is to prepare therapeutic doctors to be able to perform emergency medical skills such as resuscitation at the scene.